

Psychological Benefits of Chaurasi Pooja (Octogenarian Rite): The Priests' Perspective

Pralhad Adhikari

Abstract

Chaurasi Pooja (or Chaurasi in short) is a rite of worship commemorating the feat of a person to have witnessed at least a thousand full moons in life. As per the literal meaning, many families wait for their octogenarians' 84th birthday to celebrate it. Socioculturally, it is the ceremony to show reverence for older adults and the rite to put them in the spotlight. Six Hindu priests (or pures) from Kavre were interviewed and their responses were categorized in the framework of content analysis. The data was triangulated with three YouTube videos with other pures or pundits explaining Chaurasi and three videos of ordinary people celebrating their parents' Chaurasi. It was found that the benefits of Chaurasi Pooja can be classified into two: Religious and social-psychological. The conclusion is that Chaurasi Pooja has the religious importance of treating godlike octogenarians and clearing ways for them toward salvation or overcoming their fear of death, and the social psychological importance of revering the old person's feat to have won diseases to live as long as at least 81 years and making them feel special while inspiring older persons in their seventies to live longer.

Introduction

Old age is considered a difficult stage in life but it need not be difficult. Some older persons can live an animated life. If family members are supportive and all other aspects of senescence (such as physical activity, and cultivation of resilience factors) are balanced, old age can be as lively as the days of younger age. Being a part of society, older adults should be able to observe the rites of its culture. *Chaurasi Pooja* is one of the rituals in Nepal dedicated to older adults in their eighties. It is being practiced in Nepalese society for a long time. It is a ritual that shows others' respect for older adults and older adults' victory against diseases and frailties.

The Eighties in Developmental Psychology

Developmentalists study old age as later adulthood (60-75 years) and elderhood (75 years and above; Newman & Newman, 2012). Sociologists use the term "young old" for people aged 65-74,

“old old” for people aged 75-84, and “oldest old” for those aged 85 and above (Giddens et al., 2018, p. 303) K. Warner Schaie has proposed that there are individual differences in aging. Aging can be of three types: normal, pathological, or successful (Santrock, 2020, p. 18). In normal aging, we can observe the modest decline in psychosocial functioning through the eighties. In pathological aging, older adults show more than average decline and develop cognitive impairments like Alzheimer’s disease. Successfully aging older adults do not feel decline in physical, social, and cognitive abilities till very late in life like normally aging older persons do. If older adults can live an intellectually challenging life, they can grow cognitively even in old age.

Developmental psychology studies human development in terms of physical, cognitive, and social change in one’s life. Unlike the traditional approach, the life-span perspective assumes that there are developmental changes in old age including the eighties also. There are some peculiar developmental tasks of elderhood. In their eighties, people have lowered self-esteem (Santrock, 2019, p. 134). One-fourth of octogenarians in developed countries have active sexual life (Newman & Newman, 2012, p. 585). In old age, older adults may have to adjust to deteriorating health or even the death of a spouse, retirement and reduced income, and reduced physical strength (Hutteman et al., 2014).

Many older adults are living into their eighties and nineties of elderhood more than ever in the history of mankind (Newman & Newman, 2012, p. 564). Some people like poet Madhav Prasad Ghimire and historian Satya Mohan Joshi in Nepal also lived as centenarians and survived an active and creative life till their last days. Some people have a life span of 120 to 125 years. However, the world may not have been ready for a society with many older adults because life expectancy has increased very abruptly without society being able to prepare much (Santrock, 2020, p. 529). Nonetheless, Nepali society has an age-old tradition to offer dignity and respect to older adults. The 2011 census showed that older adults constitute more than 8% of the total population (Chalise, 2020). Those who reach their eighties are a few. Healthy aging depends on marital status and having or not having caregivers (Campos et al., 2016).

According to the socioemotional selectivity theory, people in their eighties gradually lessen their contacts with friends and relatives and maintain relationships with only close ones (Berk, 2018). A functionalist theory named disengagement theory contends that society removes people from their traditional roles so that the roles need to be freed up for others (Giddens et al., 2018, p. 299). Busy and engaged older adults are more likely to lead fulfilling lives according to activity theory. Older adults can be healthy if they do things consistent with their personality and preferences according to continuity theory (p.300).

Chaurasi Pooja as a Ritual

Chaurasi Pooja (also called *Chaurasi* or *Chaturasi*, in short) is one of the Hindu (and also Buddhist) rites to celebrate elderhood and commemorate successful aging. This is worship and is performed when an older adult becomes 84 years old generally but it is about sighting 1000 full moons. So, it is okay to perform during the early eighties. Among the Newars, it is called

Janku (pronounced जङ्कु) and is celebrated five times: in 77, 83, 88, 99, and 105 (Republica, 2019). Theoretically, Nepalese culture including religion teaches to pay homage to older people but practically, the older persons might not have been treated as well as they deserve. There are stereotypes associated with old age and ageism is rife. Sometimes, older adults are abused; a study (Acharya et al., 2021) found that more than half of older adults were abused and they were neglected and abused sexually, psychologically, financially, or physically.

Rites like *Chaurasi Pooja* are helpful to increase a member's commitment to group norms and they are also helpful to increase group cohesion (Watson-Jones & Legare, 2016). People tend to get more cooperation because of belonging to the same in-group and knowing each other through rites. They also provide feelings of shared unity (Hobson et al., 2018). Involving in religious or faith-based activities enhances the quality of life (QoL). For example, saying prayers and socializing with others help enhance QoL and the life satisfaction of older adults (Gautam et al., 2007).

After one is 81 years old, they will have already witnessed 1000 full moons. So, any full moon day after the 82nd birthday can commemorate the end of fasting of the sighting of 1000 full moons (*Chaurasi Puja Vidhi Nepali*, n.d.). It is called *sahasra purna chandra darshan puja vratodyapana* in Sanskrit (p.1). Chaurasi Pooja falls under the *Sanyas ashram* when the older persons need to exercise self-control, charity and friendliness with all according to Indian philosophy (Dwivedi, 2018). The worship consists of worship of Gods, dead ancestors, moon and planets, donation of cow, donation of money equal to the weight of older adults celebrating *Chaurasi*, and many other observances. It can last from one day to three days.

Aim and Significance of This Research

This study aimed to explore the psychosocial and sociocultural importance of *Chaurasi Pooja* and does not give much emphasis to religious aspects, especially on procedures (*pooja vidhi*). However, social factors and cultural aspects get overlapped with religious things often.

This research can reveal the psychological, social, and cultural importance of the ritual dedicated to octogenarians. There are few cultures that have cultures dedicated to older adults. One is Kōrei-sha no hi (or Keiro No Hi), the day for older adults in Japan (Joy, 2016). This study can contribute to the insight into the benefits of involving older adults, especially octogenarians, in rituals. Moreover, this study may also provide insight into the psychological and social benefits of one's involvement in traditional, social, cultural, and religious rituals. Studies of that nature are not found yet.

Methods

A convenient sample of six experienced priests (or *purohits*) from the Panauti municipality of Kavrepalanchowk district was made. They were contacted via telephone and interviewed. The interviews were recorded and analyzed in the framework of conventional content analysis (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). To triangulate, three YouTube videos of *Chaurasi* celebrations such as Ghale

Gurung (2018) were also used as data. Similarly, three videos of pundits such as Khanal (2020) explaining *Chaurasi* were used. The categories of the responses were figured out by classifying the codes derived from the interviews and videos.

Results

Old person whose *Chaurasi* is being celebrated can remain in the spotlight at least for a day. The celebration is an indication of the fact that family honors them and they have got social support as much as needed to organize a ceremony. The priests' opinions about the benefits or importance of *Chaurasi* can be sorted into two categories as shown in table 1.

Table 1
Benefits of Chaurasi Pooja

Religious importance	Social psy hological importance
Opening path to <i>Moksha</i> (or salvation)	Hope for future and about living some more years; victorious feat of living as octogenarian
Older persons become godlike: God at home; they cannot lie now on; they can bless; matter of luck (not everyone reaches this stage in life)	Satisfaction about completing religious obligation; source of joy, happiness, and content
Worshipping moon as light or knowledge; brings auspice	Source of happiness for family, neighbors, and society; Showiness, social pressure for ceremony/party on the flipside
Pleasing Gods with worship (like matrika puja), prayer and mantra recitation (like Gita, visnu sahasra nam stotra, ganesh sahasra nam stotra among others)	Bliss; celebratory mood
Singing songs (<i>bhajans</i>) dedicated to God and dancing in that joy	Honoring the elderly; other older adults get inspiration to live as long as somebody who is celebrating <i>Chaurasi</i> to be able to celebrate themselves

It is believed that octogenarians are godlike. Their newfound status of godlikeness needs a celebration. The ceremony of *Chaurasi* is important religiously because it is believed to invite the moment of *moksha* (or salvation). This observance also clears the persons in their eighties for the way to heaven where they can exist parallelly to gods. This observance has many elements

like donation (of cow, bed, wealth equal to the weight of the body, and others), worship, *havan* (burning things like ghee in fire), and recitation of mantras.

Chaturasi is about respect for older adults in their eighties. During the ceremony, they are in the spotlight. They get the attention and all relatives, friends, and neighbors come to congratulate and even worship them. Being the center of attention can please them and give them a sense of belonging and dignity. The older adults can meet many people invited to the ceremony who would otherwise have been busy with their lives. *Chaurasi* also gives the octogenarians a sense of accomplishment of fulfilling their religious obligation of a *karma* (duty). Moreover, it gives them hope and optimism that they can still live for some years on Earth to witness the colorful world and wonderful happenings herein. This ceremony marks the joy of the past and optimism about the future. It also means a sense of satisfaction because the families prove that they are ready to expend something for older adults who reared them in past. *Chaurasi* can enhance the self-esteem of older adults. They can get to re-socialize with the people they knew. They can prevent themselves from getting lonely or It is an encouragement (or *housala*) for them. It may also give a message: “You should not give up yet! Many good things like *Chaurasi* are yet to come in life!”

For the family members of octogenarians whose *Chaurasi* is being celebrated, organizing the event in itself is a challenge because many materials are to be gathered, many activities are to be done and all guests are to be welcomed and served well. Still, they take help from friends, neighbors, and relatives. The family members are also happy to have done something significant for the octogenarians. They remain busy during the ceremony to complete various activities. Other older adults who are in their seventies also get the inspiration to live as long as 81 or more to be able to do *Chaurasi*. On the flip side, the social pressure to conform to what neighbors and relatives do can create an unnecessary burden on poorer families who cannot afford such ceremonies. Otherwise, Hindu or Buddhist religions do not make *Chaurasi* compulsory; they are always optional. Moreover, all the religious, cultural, and social activities including *Chaurasi* are getting more pompous and showy. Some misbeliefs also remain about *Chaurasi*. For example, people may believe that once *Chaurasi* is celebrated, it is their time to pass away. A few sects within Hindu religion do not celebrate *Chaurasi Pooja* on various grounds.

Discussion

Those people living more than 100 years have suggested having strong willpower to live, aim for the future, faith, focus on the positive and determination not to give in to negative thoughts, enough sleep, and relaxation, a sense of humor, a moderate lifestyle, low to no ambition, something to smile at, and no worries about things we cannot control (Santrock, 2020, p. 119). Older adults satisfied with life at present are likelier to live longer. Similarly, those who derive pleasure from daily activities, find meaningfulness in life, and have an optimistic and happy attitude are likelier to survive (Lyyra et al., 2006). *Chaurasi* is an opportunity to bolster an older person’s hope, optimism, self-esteem, happiness, and sense of belongingness. Even though rituals do not have an instrumental purpose and are embedded in the larger culture of symbol or meaning, they

regulate emotions, performance goal states, and social connections (Hobson et al., 2018). Rites are predefined sequences of activities and they are rigid, formal, and repetitive.

The significance of *Chaurasi Pooja* should also be evaluated in a sociohistorical context. The time of the society it began was probably when the life expectancy was too short, and sighting 1000 moons would be a great feat. Now, science and technology have advanced very much that many medical crises in life are overcome and people definitely live longer than when they would be absent. Still, psychological crises and disturbed social order (like by emigration of children abroad) can contribute to bad mental health experiences in old age. In Nepalese society where the average life expectancy is still 71 years, being able to hold *Chaurasi Pooja* is no less a feat yet.

Conclusion

From a social-psychological perspective, ceremonies like *Chaurasi Pooja* can be an antidote against loneliness that can be emotional or relational (or social; Giddens et al., 2018, p.304). Social connections can promote happiness in the lives of older adults (Waldinger & Schulz, 2010). Ceremonies or rites like *Chaurasi* can compensate for the loss caused by crises like the death of spouse or invasion of some disease likely to be chronic or incurable. One crisis in the life of octogenarians or nonagenarians may induce another crisis (Newman & Newman, 2012, p. 573). For example, the death of a spouse can lead to insomnia, loss of hunger and motivation, and decline in physical activity. These declines may result in biological lethargy.

Aago tapnu mudhako, kura sunnu bhudha ko (a proverb popular in Nepal that means: burn a log for heat, listen to older persons for wit) and such beliefs reflect that Nepalese society, culture, and tradition have been respectful to older persons. The *Chaurasi* ceremony is another unit in that culture of veneration to older adults. It is also a celebration for a person who has achieved the feat of witnessing a thousand full moons in their life. Nepal seems welcoming to long life (and old age is its part and parcel) reflected in blessings like *Chiranjivi bhavah* (Sanskrit phrase that means: Live long!) or *bisha shay aayu hos* (Nepali blessing that means: May you live for 2000 years!). Similar is the ancient beliefs in the Indian subcontinent reflected in the verse: *Pashyem sharadah shatam, Jivet sharadah shatam* (Dwivedi, 2018) from *Atharva veda* which means: May we be able to see and live a hundred autumns!

References

- Acharya, S. R., Suman, B. K., Pahari, S., Shin, Y. C., & Moon, D. H. (2021). Prevalence of abuse among the elderly population of Syangja, Nepal. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1), 1348. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-11417-0>
- Berk, L. E. (2018). *Development through the lifespan* (7th ed.). Pearson.
- Campos, A. C. V., Ferreira, E. F., Vargas, A. M. D., & Gonçalves, L. H. T. (2016). Healthy aging profile in octogenarians in Brazil. *Revista Latino-Americana de Enfermagem*, 24, e2724. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1518-8345.0694.2724>
- Chalise, H. N. (2020). Provincial situation of elderly population in Nepal. *American Journal of Aging Science and Research*, 1(1), 9–11.
- Chaurasi Puja Vidhi Nepali*. (n.d.). <https://ia803102.us.archive.org/9/items/chaursi/Chaurasi-Puja-Vidhi-Nepali.pdf>
- Dwivedi, A. V. (2018). Old Age. In P. Jain, R. Sherma, & M. Khanna (Eds.), *Hinduism and tribal religions: Encyclopedia of Indian religions*. Springer Netherlands. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-024-1036-5_620-1
- Gautam, R., Saito, T., & Kai, I. (2007). Leisure and religious activity participation and mental health: gender analysis of older adults in Nepal. *BMC Public Health*, 7(1), 299. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-7-299>
- Ghale Gurung, B. (2018). *Long Life Celebration In Nepal/ Chaurasi Puja* [Video]. YouTube. <https://youtu.be/RFiaQOkz8eU?t=580>
- Giddens, A., Duneier, M., Appelbaum, R. P., & Carr, D. (2018). *Introduction to sociology* (11th ed.). W. W. Norton & Company.
- Hobson, N. M., Schroeder, J., Risen, J. L., Xygalatas, D., & Inzlicht, M. (2018). The psychology of rituals: An integrative review and process-based framework. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088868317734944>
- Hsieh, H. F., & Shannon, S. E. (2005). Three approaches to qualitative content analysis. *Qualitative Health Research*, 15(9), 1277–1288. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732305276687>
- Hutteman, R., Hennecke, M., Orth, U., Reitz, A. K., & Specht, J. (2014). Developmental tasks as a framework to study personality development in adulthood and old age. *European Journal of Personality*, 28(3), 267–278.
- Joy, A. (2016). *What Is Japan's "Respect For The Aged Day"?* <https://theculturetrip.com/japan/articles/how-to-spend-respect-for-the-aged-day/>
- Khanal, D. (2020). *Chaurasi Pooja Method and Materials (in Nepali)* [Video]. YouTube. <https://youtu.be/ugKn0YHkto?t=1>

- Lyyra, T.-M., Törmäkangas, T. M., Read, S., Rantanen, T., & Berg, S. (2006). Satisfaction with present life predicts survival in octogenarians. *The Journals of Gerontology: Series B*, 61(6), P319–P326. <https://doi.org/10.1093/geronb/61.6.P319>
- Newman, B. M., & Newman, P. R. (2012). *Development through life: A psychosocial approach* (11th ed.). Wadsworth, Cengage Learning.
- Republica. (2019). *What is Newari tradition “Janku” about? (with video)*. <https://myrepublica.nagariknetwork.com/news/suryaman-completed-his-one-thousand-full-moon/>
- Santrock, J. W. (2019). *Adolescence* (17th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Santrock, J. W. (2020). *A topical approach to lifespan development* (10th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Waldinger, R. J., & Schulz, M. S. (2010). What’s love got to do with it? Social functioning, perceived health, and daily happiness in married octogenarians. *Psychology and Aging*, 25(2), 422–431. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0019087>
- Watson-Jones, R. E., & Legare, C. H. (2016). The social functions of group rituals. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 25(1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721415618486>

अभौतिक संस्कृति

A Journal of Intangible Culture

वर्ष : ७

अङ्क : ७

वर्ष : २०८०

नेपाल सरकार

संस्कृति, पर्यटन तथा नागरिक उड्डयन मन्त्रालय

सिंहदरबार, काठमाडौं

संरक्षक

सुरेश अधिकारी, सचिव

सम्पादक सल्लाहकार

प्रा.डा. वीणा पौड्याल

प्रधान सम्पादक

डा. सुरेश सुरस श्रेष्ठ, सहसचिव

सम्पादन मण्डल

पुण्यमाया गुरागाई, उपसचिव

सविता कुमारी जोशी, पुरातत्त्व अधिकृत

राजकुमार दुलाल, शाखा अधिकृत

नारायणप्रसाद खनाल, शाखा अधिकृत

रामकृष्ण महर्जन, छविकार

प्रकाशक

संस्कृति, पर्यटन तथा नागरिक उड्डयन मन्त्रालय, सिंहदरवार, काठमाडौं

फोन नं. : ०१-४२११५०५, ०१-४२११५५६

वेबसाइट : www.tourism.gov.np

ISSN No: 2717-4859

9 772717 485005

आवरण चित्र : रामकृष्ण महर्जन (साकेला नाच गर्नुपूर्व किरात राईका धामीद्वारा साकेलाथान देवताको पूजा, खोटाङ, हलेसी)

प्रकाशन मिति : २०८० साल आषाढ

प्रकाशन प्रति : ५००

मुद्रक : एनीटाइम प्रिन्टिङ प्रेस (०१-५५१४८३२)

प्रस्तुत लेखहरूमा व्यक्त भएका विचार नेपाल सरकारको नीति वा यस मन्त्रालयको आधिकारिक धारणा नभई लेखकका नितान्त व्यक्तिगत धारणा वा विचार हुन् ।

सम्पादकीय

संस्कृति मानव र मानवीय स्वभावको परिचायक हो, जो निरन्तर मानव सभ्यता र समाज विकासको सम्वाहकका रूपमा रहँदै आएको छ। सम्पदा यसैको प्रतिविम्ब हो, जसलाई हरेक मानव र उसको समाजले आफ्नो पहिचानको रूपमा स्वीकारिसकेको छ। तसर्थ, मानव सभ्यता र समाजको सम्वाहक र आफ्नो पहिचानलाई अक्षुण्ण राख्न मानिस अर्वाचिन समयदेखि नै निरन्तर लागि रहेको छ, विभिन्न भावभङ्गी अनि स्वरूप र शैलीमा।

प्रकारान्तरले मानववि कासको चरमोत्कर्षमा आइपुगेको यस एकाइसौं शताब्दीमा उल्लेखित आफ्नो पहिचानलाई विभिन्न कारण र पक्षहरूले नकारात्मक असर पार्दै, अक्षुण्णतालाई कायम राख्ने प्रयासहरू आ-आफ्नो सन्दर्भमा विभिन्न तह र स्तरबाट स्वभाविक रूपमा हुने गर्दछ। सोही सन्दर्भ र विषयवस्तुमा केन्द्रीत रही बहुजातीय, बहुभाषिक, बहुधार्मिक र बहुसांस्कृतिक नेपालका विभिन्न किसिमका अनुपम संस्कृति र सांस्कृतिक सम्पदाहरूलाई जनसमुदाय स्तरबाट संरक्षण गर्दै निरन्तरता दिइरहेको भएतापनि राज्य वा सरकारले यसलाई अभि प्राथमिकता दिई सुव्यवस्थित गर्नुपर्ने महसुस गरी अन्य क्रियाकलापका अतिरिक्त खोज अध्ययन अनुसन्धान एवं अभिलेखन कार्यलाई विशेष प्राथमिकता दिदै आएको छ। तसर्थ, विगत छ वर्षदेखि अमूर्त सांस्कृतिक सम्पदा सम्बन्धी विविध पक्षहरूलाई समेट्ने गरी यो **अमूर्त संस्कृति (A Journal of Intangible Culture)**को प्रकाशनलाई यस मन्त्रालयले निरन्तरता दिदै आइरहेको छ। यसै सिलसिलामा यस वर्ष **अमूर्त संस्कृतिको** सातौं अंक प्रकाशन गर्न पाउँदा असाध्यै खुशी लागेको छ।

नेपालमा शताब्दीयौंदेखि चलनचल्तीमा रहेका हाम्रा अनुपम संस्कृति तथा हाम्रो पहिचानको रूपमा रहेका अभौतिक सांस्कृतिक सम्पदाका विभिन्न आयामहरूमा खोज अनुसन्धान सहितका प्रामाणिक तत्वहरूलाई समेटेर तयार पारिएका विभिन्न विद्वान् लेखकका लेख रचनाहरूलाई समावेश गरिएको यस प्रकाशनले यस विधासँग सम्बन्धित पेशाकर्मी, प्राध्यापक, विद्यार्थी लगायत यस विषयमा चासो राख्ने जो कोहीलाई पनि उपयुक्त जानकारी उपलब्ध गर्न मद्दत पुग्ने छ भन्ने अपेक्षा मन्त्रालयले राखेको छ भने यस सम्बन्धी कुनै किसिमको राय सुझाव वा टिप्पणी भएमा उपलब्ध गराउनु हुनेछ भन्ने समेत आशा गरिएको छ।

अन्ततः यस प्रकाशनका लागि आफ्नो महत्वपूर्ण अध्ययन अनुसन्धानमूलक लेख रचनाहरू उपलब्ध गराई दिनु भएकोमा सम्पूर्ण विद्वत वर्गमा हार्दिक कृतज्ञता व्यक्त गर्न चाहन्छु। साथै जर्नल प्रकाशनका लागि निरन्तर लागीपरेर सहयोग गर्नु हुने सम्पूर्ण सम्पादक मण्डल तथा यस मन्त्रालय संस्कृति महाशाखाका सम्पूर्ण राष्ट्रसेवक कर्मचारी साथीहरूमा हार्दिक धन्यवाद एवं आभार व्यक्त गर्दछु।

डा. सुरेश सुरस श्रेष्ठ

प्रधान सम्पादक तथा संस्कृति महाशाखा प्रमुख

Indigenous Knowledge: Review from Climate Change Adaptation Perspective

Mukesh Dangol

११९

Psychological Benefits of Chaurasi Pooja (Octogenarian Rite): The Priests' Perspective

Pralhad Adhikari

१२९

A Study of Surjyang culture in Sherpa: an Intangible Attribute

Anglami Sherpa, Lecturer and PhD. Scholar

१३७

Varaha Avatar Of Kartik Naach: A Sacred Dance Drama Of Lord Vishnu

Suraj Shakya

१४६